

DIRECTIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. Increasing the economic efficiency of agriculture, first of all, serves to fulfill the requirements of the country's food strategy directions and ensure food safety. Also, on the other hand, this goal will be achieved through the rational use of the available labor, land, water, material and financial resources of the cotton-growing enterprises, regardless of the forms of ownership, based on the improvement of economic relations between them.

Keywords: economic efficiency, profitability, main indicators, system, benefit, material cost, income, crop area, gross product, fertility, net profit, cotton fiber, financial means.

One of the main requirements of the current period is not only the production of raw materials in agriculture, including cotton, but also the proper and effective implementation of its processing and sale. Because the main part of the added value created, that is, the income, is formed in the following areas. In our republic, the issues of using cotton raw materials, cotton fiber, cotton oil, gas and other cotton products have been solved separately. However, starting from 2017, the formation of the cotton-textile cluster puts on the agenda to solve the issues of increasing the efficiency of the multi-stage complex system in the process from plowing the land to planting, care and production of finished products from raw materials.

Based on the opinions and opinions of scientists who have conducted research on the methodology of economic efficiency evaluation until now, they can be conditionally divided into two groups. Scientists belonging to the first group believe that the criterion indicator of economic efficiency should be the only one. According to them, this indicator has a general characteristic and should objectively and fully reflect economic efficiency. The second group of economists advocates that economic efficiency should be determined through a system of indicators.

From this point of view, every economic scientist put forward their scientifically based opinions and judgments, based on the period of studying the

problems in this field and the forms of economic management, in researching the issues of cotton cultivation development.

R.V.Abdullaev in relation to the issues of development of cotton cultivation, the development of cotton cultivation will mainly depend on two factors, i.e. increase of productivity and expansion of cotton fields. The level of productivity depends on the natural and climatic conditions of a particular country, the degree of mechanization of cotton cultivation, the extent to which scientific achievements are applied to production, and other intensive factors. From this point of view, it can be concluded that while the development of cotton cultivation and the achievement of an increase in production are carried out mainly on the basis of intensive factors in the conditions of transition to market relations, this process occurs as a result of the effect of the combination of extensive factors.

Q. Khasanjanov and A. Toshmatov scientifically justify the importance and essence of using intensive technology in the network in the development of cotton production. they interpret it as acceleration of development. Such one-sided interpretation is found in scientific literature and in practice, and as a result, various approaches to intensive technology are taking place. If the intensive technology in cotton farming is approached as interrelated technological and organizational activities aimed at growing the most and quality crops with less labor and money from a specific cotton area, then the above opinion is true. Because it is a mistake to look at intensive technology only on the basis of the factor of mechanization.

A. Abdiev put forward the opinion that "the development of cotton farming is related to the issues of reducing the number of people employed in the production of cotton raw materials based on the gradual formation of industries that turn cotton raw materials into finished products." Although the basis of this opinion is related to the formation of entities that turn cotton raw materials into finished products and the process of providing them with labor force in the process of gradually attracting workers employed in the agricultural sector to industrial enterprises in the context of the transition to market relations, if this issue is approached scientifically, the reduction of the number of workers in cotton production cannot be considered as a factor that directly affects the development of the industry. Because cotton farming is a labor-intensive industry, and at the same time, the reduction in the number of workers can have a negative effect on the timely implementation of agro-technological activities in cotton cultivation. On this basis, this is not an event implemented through short-

term programs, but is considered an evolutionary process, which will be implemented step by step based on the formation of private ownership in the network.

A. Burkhanov noted that "the development of cotton farming directly depends on the development of cotton seeds." We believe that it is correct to approach this issue from a scientific point of view along with all other factors in the development of the network. Because cotton growers sow high-quality seeds of fast-ripening, high-yielding varieties that are compatible with the natural and climatic conditions is the primary basis for the effectiveness of factors affecting the development of cotton cultivation. Based on the principles of the market economy, we can conclude that the development of the cotton complex, which is of decisive importance for the country's economy in modern economic conditions, gives a strong impetus to the development of raw materials and industrial sectors. This is also evident in the experience of developed countries. From this point of view, encouraging the development of the cotton complex and increasing its competitiveness is important for the national economic interests of our country. Support for the development of the cotton complex can become the basis for the development of other structural complexes of the national economy. We believe that the future development and increase of competitiveness of the cotton industry along the added value chain represents a model that will contribute to the country's economic development.

The cotton complex occupies an important place in the process of socio-economic development, and it is of great importance for the economy of the country, which dominates its successful development. Cotton products processed in factories are very important raw materials for the light and food industry. Cotton products are also used in heavy industry. Up to 300 types of consumer products and technical products are made from cotton raw materials. In the economy of our country, the weight of cotton growing and cotton ginning industry is large. As the industry develops, other sectors of the national economy will also develop. From this point of view, further development of cotton growing is considered one of the priorities of our republic. It is known that our country has long been famous for its climate, senmiun soil, underground and surface resources. The main factor for achieving such success is the constant attention paid to the sector by our government, and especially economic benefits, scientific and technical achievements and the introduction of advanced technologies, opening a big way for the farming movement. Thanks to

the gradual reforms, the material and technical base of farms is getting stronger year by year.

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